

FOODITY

D3.2 – FOODITY Programme Services v2

Prepared by Sploro

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet Of Things
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MM	Monthly Follow-Up Meetings
PCs	Pitch Contests
PEM	Progress Evaluation Meetings
RTOs	Research And Technology Organisations
SMEs	Small And Medium-Sized Enterprises
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities And Threats

ABSTRACT

This document is deliverable D3.2 – FOODITY Programme Services v2. The objective of this deliverable is to address the training Programme that will be provided to the companies selected in the 2nd open call of the FOODITY project. This is the second edition of the training Programme, which has been refined and enhanced based on the lessons learned from the first edition. The improvements aim to better meet the needs of the participating companies. and ensure more effective outcomes.

The FOODITY Project

The main goal of [FOODITY](#) is to create a European ecosystem of digital solutions that contributes to a more sustainable and healthy food and nutrition system — respecting citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty.

FOODITY will run a **2M€ pilot development Programme for creating 12 data-driven solutions** to demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while guaranteeing the user's full control and ownership over their personal data.

These innovations will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the four Food 20301 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: (1) Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (2) Food systems supporting a healthy planet, (3) Circularity and resource efficiency, and (4) Innovation and empowering communities.

Participants in the pilot development Programme will be selected through two open calls to be launched in July and October 2023, respectively. Eligible beneficiaries will be research and technology organisations (RTOs) and universities, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), social innovation actors and training organisations.

The Programme will provide its beneficiaries with a set of value-added services: from one-to-one mentoring to training on technical, business, and legal matters, as well as technical and financial support (up to 187.500€ per beneficiary) for developing their pilots.

During the next 3 years (January 2023 - December 2025), the FOODITY consortium, comprised of 7 partners, will join forces to make this a reality.

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Executive summary

This document, **Deliverable D3.2 – FOODITY Programme Services v2**, provides a comprehensive overview of the activities and services designed for the third parties selected through FOODITY – Open Call #2, who will participate in the FOODITY Programme. The Programme is part of Work Package 3, and it's focused on delivering essential technical and business-oriented support, aimed at empowering the selected projects to reach their goals and maximize their impact in key domains.

As in the first Programme, the main objective of the second FOODITY Programme is to offer a wide range of value-added services to the FOODITY Innovators. The activities from the first batch worked well, so the Programme will maintain the same type of activities: specialised technical and business group trainings, individual sessions with the experts, group coaching sessions for citizen awareness, and regular mentoring sessions.

Moreover, the Programme will integrate the lessons learned from 1st edition of the FOODITY Programme to refine and enhance its offerings. By leveraging the insights and feedback gathered from the first Programme Innovators, the second FOODITY Programme will implement improvements that are expected to better meet the needs of its participants. This iterative approach ensures that the support provided is continually optimised, benefiting from the experience and knowledge gained from previous initiatives.

1. Lessons learned from the first FOODITY Programme

The first edition of the FOODITY Programme is currently running, having launched in January 2024 and will end in December 2024.

The objective of the first FOODITY Programme was to offer a wide range of value-added services to the 6 FOODITY Innovators funded through the first open call. For this second edition, the same objective is maintained.

More than halfway through the first FOODITY Programme, the team has learned a number of lessons that it intends to implement during the second edition of the Programme. The lessons learned have been divided into different sections to facilitate their implementation in the Programme:

1. Lessons learned on the **Programme Structure**

- **Modularity and flexibility:** The beneficiaries of the Programme suggested changes be made to the structure, as they would have preferred to have the first month and a half of the Programme focused on discussing and updating KPIs and adjusting the technical requirements. During the first edition, one monthly topic is being delivered by the experts from month 1 to month 9. This was considered somewhat overwhelming by the Innovators, and it was therefore decided to leave the first month and a half for the setting of KPIs and technical topics. As a solution, two business topics will be carried out together in the same month.

2. Lessons learned on the **Technical support**

- **Technological adaptation:** The Programme has revealed that not all beneficiaries have the same level of technological competence, suggesting the need to adapt technical support at different levels. During the first edition, a joint session was followed by individual sessions. During this second batch, the dynamic is the same but more personalised, considering all the needs and the starting point of the solution's innovation.

3. Lessons learned on **Impact and Sustainability**

- **Measuring impact:** After monitoring the Programme through monthly online mentoring sessions and monthly satisfaction surveys carried out by mentors and mentees through the Sploro platform, it has been seen as crucial to have clear metrics from the outset to assess the impact of the Programme in terms of capacity building, creation of new initiatives, or citizen engagement. In the first Programme, the same scale was not always used to evaluate the parameters during the monthly evaluations, which made it difficult to monitor the satisfaction of the Innovators

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during all the months in a more consistent manner, as the scale was different. In the second batch, the aim is to have the same scale of measurement for each criterion during each month (e.g. standard 1-5 Likert scale).

4. Lessons learned on **Sploro Platform**

- **Material extension:** Although innovators received a complete manual about the functioning of the Sploro's Platform at the beginning of the Programme, it has been seen as essential a training session before starting the whole course. An optional session will be proposed, or a demo recording will be distributed with additional information to the manual already provided.

5. Lessons learned on **Communication and Monitoring**

- **Single communication channel:** It has been found that the Sploro platform is not always intuitive for messaging between the FOODITY consortium and the Innovators, so email will be the primary channel used for communication and the platform will be used for tracking KPIs and as a repository for all course materials.

Considering all these lessons learned, the second FOODITY Programme has been modified to be more adapted to the beneficiaries of the 2nd FOODITY Open Call. A description of the Programme with the changes already implemented is given below. This description is a summary, since the full description of the Programme was provided in Deliverable 3.1. Where more information is provided in comparison to the first deliverable, it is indicated in the text.

2. FOODITY Programme overall description

As mentioned above, this document describes the activities designed for the third parties that will be selected through the 2nd FOODITY Open Call. It is based on the good practices from the first Programme and on the lessons learnt in order to implement them and improve the content of the second FOODITY Programme.

As a crucial component of Work Package 3, **this Programme provides vital technical and business-oriented support to help the selected projects achieve their goals and maximise their impact in key areas.** The primary objective of the FOODITY Programme is to offer beneficiaries a broad spectrum of **value-added services**, creating an environment conducive to the successful development of their projects. To this end, the Programme includes specialised training, group coaching, general webinars, and access to additional resources, all aimed at enhancing participants' skills and knowledge.

2.1. FOODITY Programme services packages

As in the first FOODITY Programme, the second batch of FOODITY Innovators will have **four distinct categories of support.** These categories cover:

- **Financial support**
- **FOODITY Capacity Building Services which includes:**
 - **Business support**
 - **Mentoring follow up**
- **Technical Support Services**
- **Group coaching activities related to social impact and initiatives**

This method ensures a holistic approach to meet the diverse needs of the beneficiaries. More information is described in the following sections, and for further details, consider Deliverable 3.1, where all the services are explained in detail.

2.2. Programme timeline

The dynamics of the programme timeline will be the same in this second edition, as it worked well in the first programme: a well-structured and systematic approach to its operations, known as the "funnel approach," which serves as a roadmap for its functioning and will consist of 12 months divided into two phases. The approach is graphically represented in [Figure 1. FOODITY funnel approach for open calls](#), providing a visual depiction of the different phases involved in the Programme.

Figure 1. FOODITY funnel approach for open calls

Each phase of the funnel in the Programme is structured to ensure a comprehensive and organised progression:

- In **Phase 1** (9 months), the process is subdivided into three distinct stages, each with a specific purpose and set of activities:
 - **Specification and Design**, which entails the detailed conceptualisation and planning of the proposed initiatives.
 - **Implementation**, which is dedicated to the practical realisation of the planned activities, putting the ideas into action.
 - **Validation and Certification**, which focuses on evaluating the outcomes and verifying their alignment with predetermined standards.
- In **Phase 2** (3 months), the primary focus is to maximise impact and guarantee the long-term sustainability of the beneficiaries. This phase involves activities geared towards scaling up successful initiatives, fine-tuning strategies, and creating a framework that ensures the project's continued relevance and effectiveness.

Between the two phases, a **Mid-term Pitch** will take place to externally evaluate and select the top three projects from Phase 1 and advance them to Phase 2. During this event, the beneficiaries will showcase the pilot projects they have developed to a panel of external evaluators. At the end of Phase 2, a **final event** will be organised to select the best project after the presentation of the results of this last phase.

An extended description of each of the phases and the evaluation criteria is provided in Deliverable 3.1.

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Figure 2. Timeline overview

3. FOODITY Capacity Building Services

The Capacity Building Services Programme is a dynamic and inclusive plan designed to empower the selected teams with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to thrive in today's rapidly evolving landscape. Recognising the importance of ongoing learning and professional development, this Programme offers a holistic approach to capacity building, catering to the diverse needs and aspirations of participants.

3.1. Roles

The FOODITY Programme involves different stakeholders, which can be divided into three main groups:

- **FOODITY Innovators** (also called beneficiaries), which are the teams selected from the 2nd Open Call)
- **Consortium Partners**, which are the FOODITY Partners in charge of providing technical and mentoring support, and
- **Topic-Specific External Experts**, which are external experts in different fields providing business topics and coaching sessions.

Deliverable 3.1 provides further details about the responsibilities of each group.

3.2. Methodology

The methodology consists of a structured learning framework:

(1) Business monthly topics guided by accomplished experts. Following the exploration of each topic, external experts will guide participants in the better understanding of the topic and use that information through **(2) individual sessions**.

During the first Programme, the topics were conducted on a monthly basis. This implied that the Innovators had a joint session and another one individually from month 1 to month 9. Based on one of the lessons learned, which collects the opinions of some Innovators and the feedback requests, there is a preference to start the monthly topics in month 2, having the first one to set the technicalities and the first report. So, two topics will be delivered on month 3 in the second Programme: The Business Strategy and the Business Modelling. This will give them time to properly define the KPIs and to set up the technical part together with the consortium partners.

According to the feedback requests filled in by the Innovators, all the external experts received positive evaluations. Therefore, the consortium has decided to continue their participation whenever possible. As such, experts and topics will be the same as in the first batch of the

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Programme. In cases where an expert is not available to repeat their role in the second Programme, other experts that participated in an expression for interest will be contacted. The update distribution of monthly topics for the second FOODITY Programme is represented in Figure 3. Proposal calendar for business topics:

Figure 3. Proposal calendar for business topics

(3) Monitoring sessions to monitor the progress and impact of the Programme on the participants, as well as the correct implementation of the pilots with SPLORO and F6S. These contact points will provide continuous monitoring and support throughout the Programme, ensuring that participating organisations make progress towards their objectives and milestones. These sessions are held on a monthly basis and take place online. During these sessions, the strengths and weaknesses of the teams are reviewed, any questions that may have arisen during the month are discussed and requests from the Innovators are heard to take action to improve the programme.

(4) A double evaluation will be carried out. Firstly, external experts will provide feedback on the development of the funded experiments and make recommendations for future actions at the end of each month. Secondly, both external experts and mentees will independently rate the sessions, yielding a quantitative analysis of the progress made in the areas under focus.

4. Technical Support Services

Within the context of the FOODITY Programme, the Technical Support Services stand as a pivotal pillar, dedicated to equipping participants with the technical acumen necessary for successful project implementation. These services, carefully curated to align with the diverse needs of the FOODITY Innovators, include the following:

- **Onboarding Meeting** – Online (around mid-November 2024)
- **Technical Documentation**
 - Will be sent to the selected teams at the beginning of the programme.
- **Technical Mentoring Sessions:**
 - **Topic 1. Technologies for Data Collection and Data Processing of Food and Nutrition Data - Online**
 - **Topic 2. Personal Data Sovereignty – Online**
 - **Topic 3. Technologies and Standards for Providing Users Control of Their Personal Data - Online**
 - **Topic 4. Data Ethics Assessment – Online**

Dates for these sessions will be defined before the start of the programme in November 2024.

- **Ticketing system**

This support is provided by the technical partners of FOODITY consortium. **JIBE** will be responsible for the implementation of the Ticketing and provide the necessary support services, while **SOB** and **CERTH** will oversee monitoring the response metrics and report to the coordination on the overall progress and any relevant incidents that occur during the process. This includes collecting data on response times for ticket resolution, evaluating the level of effectiveness in problem resolution, and assessing the overall performance of technical partners in addressing requests from funded third parties.

Figure 4. Technical Support overview

5. Group coaching activities

Group coaching is designed and provided by ZSI to assist the beneficiaries in recognising their specific challenges and developing clear and practical solutions to achieve their goals. The coaching activities are centred around leveraging the expertise of the pilot teams and providing individual support to create tailored solutions for their challenges. By following a systemic coaching approach, the Programme helps participants identify the issues and obstacles they may encounter during their pilot development processes.

The coaching process includes three rounds of reflection and solution-building:

- **Group coaching 1: 28th Nov. 2024**
 - Setting: face-to-face, back-to-back with the training event, ~ 6 hours
 - Aim: Pilot beneficiaries identify topics and challenges they might face in phase 1 and are supported in finding solutions and successfully kicking off their pilot development processes.
- **Group coaching 2: 06th March 2025**
 - Setting: online, ~ 4 hours
 - Aim: The teams adapt their goals and identify new topics and challenges to find further solutions based on their experiences in the first 6 months of pilot development.
- **Group coaching 3: (Month 9 of 2nd batch)**
 - Setting: face-to-face, after the pitching event, ~ 3 hours
 - Aim: Pilot beneficiaries identify topics and challenges they might face in phase 2 and are supported in finding solutions.

BEGINNING PHASE 1

One day f2f training on citizen engagement processes in pilot development will be implemented for each call beneficiary team (M12 and M25).

HALF PHASE 1

At half time of phase 1 (M16 and M30) a second group coaching will be implemented online. Here the teams have the possibility to adapt their goals and identify new topics and challenges to find further solutions based on their experiences in the first 6 month of pilot development.

BEGINNING PHASE 2

Two last group coaching will be conducted back to back with the pitching events, where the three winning pilot beneficiaries of each call beneficiary group will participate.

Figure 5. Timeline description of coaching activities

6. Description of the Sploro platform

The Sploro platform (<https://cascadefunding.sploro.eu/>) will be used in the framework of the 2nd FOODITY Programme. It is a complete, dynamic and fully customisable platform, which allows not only the monitoring and follow-up of the teams, but also the generation of an integrated system in which all the different actors of the Programme can interact, including the presentation and sharing of materials and courses and the exchange of deliverables. It has been successful and has been positively evaluated, but it also has room for improvement as some Innovators have raised concerns at some point. This is why it has been necessary to schedule an optional meeting with the Innovators specifically to explain details about the platform. This session will be recorded and sent to everyone as complementary material to the Platform Manual in order to avoid any problems with the platform.

Deliverable 3.1 provides relevant details about the onboarding process, the access to the joint sessions, the individual sessions schedule and other features.

7. Final Considerations

The FOODITY Programme Services (v2) of the FOODITY project is the second of two services catalogues and is addressed to the applicants of the second open call, so that they know what they can expect from the FOODITY Programme.

D3.2 serves as a comprehensive overview of the various dimensions that constitute the second FOODITY Programme. From its inception, the deliverable's objective has been to provide a detailed understanding of the Programme's core elements, methodologies, and approaches, equipping stakeholders with a holistic view of what to anticipate during their participation.

This deliverable has been produced considering what has worked in the past edition and has been updated with the experiences, challenges and successes encountered by the consortium in the first round. This iterative approach ensures that the FOODITY Programme is not a static content, but a living and evolving initiative that responds to the ever-changing needs and aspirations of its participants.

	Programme 1	Programme 2
Programme structure	Monthly topics, one expert per topic, delivered from month 1 to month 9.	Two business topics (Business Strategy and Business Modelling) delivered in the same month.
Technical Support	Joint session followed by individual sessions for technical support, without specific adaptation to individual needs.	More personalised technical support considering the different technological levels of participants.
Evaluation process	Evaluation lacked consistent metrics throughout the months, using varying scales.	Standardised evaluation process with a consistent 1-5 Likert scale used throughout.
Monitoring	Monthly online mentoring sessions, surveys to assess progress.	Similar structure, but with improvements in tracking progress and satisfaction using consistent evaluation scales.
Platform (Sploro)	Platform used for monitoring and communication but had issues with intuitiveness.	Optional training session or demo recording added to improve understanding of the Sploro platform.
Communication	Communication primarily through the Sploro platform, which was not always intuitive.	Email adopted as the primary communication channel, with Sploro used for tracking and repository purposes.

Deliverable 3.2 also serves as a summary document containing the lessons learned from the first FOODITY Programme.